

filtered, crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b. p. 60–80°) mixture and characterised as 2 (Table 1).

Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss Specord 75 spectrophotometer.

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A Simple Method of Oximation. Transformation of Steroidal Nitroolefins to Ketoximes

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METHODS are reported for the transformation of nitroolefins into ketoximes^{1,2}. Some of these methods are rather drastic. This communication describes a simple method using methylamine, zinc dust for the conversion of 6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1), its 3 β -chloro (2) and 3 β -acetoxy analogues (3) into 5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (4), 3 β -chloro (5) and 3 β -acetoxy (6) ketoximes in 78–85% yields.

Experimental

To a well stirred solution of 6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) dissolved in ether-methanol (50 ml; 1:1) containing methylamine (15.0 ml, 40% in H₂O), zinc dust (3.0 g) was added at room temperature. The change of colour in ~1 h indicated the completion of the reaction and was also monitored by tlc. The reaction mixture was filtered into a separating funnel containing water and washed with water several times. The ethereal solution was dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous) and evaporated. The semi-solid thus obtained was re-crystallised to give 5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (4) (780 mg, 78%), m.p. 197° (lit⁶. 197–98°). Under similar reaction conditions, nitroolefins 2 and 3 provided ketoximes 5 (800 mg, 80%), m.p. 173° (lit⁶. 175°) and 6 (850 mg, 85%), m.p. 200° (lit⁷. 201°).

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Condensed 1,8-Naphthyridines. Part-VII.

Synthesis of 6H-Indeno[1,2-b][1,8]-naphthyridin-6-one

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of 2,3 fused^{1–4} and substituted^{5–7} 1,8-naphthyridines, we report in this note the synthesis of the hitherto unreported 6H-indeno[1,2-b][1,8]naphthyridin-6-one.

The starting compound 2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid (I) was obtained by the alkaline hydrolysis of 3-cyano-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine, which in turn obtained by the condensation

of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (3) with benzoylacetonitrile in the presence of piperidine⁹. Cyclisation of 1 with concentrated sulphuric acid resulted in the formation of 6*H*-indeno[1,2-*b*] [1,8]naphthyridin-6-one (2) in good yield. The formation of the same compound (2) was confirmed by the unambiguous synthesis involving the Friedlander's condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (3) with indane-1,3-dione (4), in the presence of ethanol containing a catalytic amount of piperidine. The compounds obtained by the two methods were identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

The structure assignment of 2 was based on elemental analysis and spectral (ir, mass and pmr) data. Formation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and a strong band at 1720 cm^{-1} in its ir spectrum indicated the presence of carbonyl group. The spectrum also exhibited bands at 1600, 1460, 1400, 1380, 1220, 1190, 1090, 980, 950, 930, 880, 780 and 730 cm^{-1} . In the mass spectra, the molecular ion peak was observed at m/z 232 which corresponds to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}$. The pmr spectrum was also in agreement with the proposed structure.

Experimental

The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested by tlc. Ir spectrum (nujol) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, pmr spectrum (CDCl_3) on a 100 MHz Varian spectrometer using TMS as internal reference, and mass spectrum on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument.

3-Cyano-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine: It was prepared by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (3) with benzoylacetonitrile by the method of Hawes and Wibberley⁹ in 80% yield, m.p. 223 (lit. 224–25°).

2-Phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid (1): A solution of potassium hydroxide (2 g) in water (2 ml) was added to a solution of 3-cyano-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine (1 g) in ethanol (20 ml) and the solution was heated under reflux for 14 h. The ethanol was evaporated on a steam-bath, then water (20 ml) added, and the solution acidified with glacial

acetic acid to yield the acid (70%), m.p. 260° (lit.⁹ 259–60).

6*H*-Indeno[1,2-*b*] [1,8]naphthyridin-6-one (2): *Method-A:* Compound 1 (1 g) and concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml) were heated on a water-bath for 3 h. The solution was cooled and poured onto crushed ice and basified with ammonia solution. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, (50%), m.p. 278° (Found: C, 77.49; H, 3.41; N, 12.01. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}$ requires: C, 77.85; H, 3.44; N, 12.06%); 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 61.08; H, 2.89; N, 20.32. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_8\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 61.16; H, 2.91; N, 20.38%). *Method-B:* A mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (3; 0.1 mol) and indene-1,3-dione (4; 0.1 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (30 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of piperidine for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, and the separated solid filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

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Synthesis of 2,3-Dihydro-5,7-dihydroxy-8-(γ,γ dimethylallyl)-2-(4'-hydroxy-2'-methoxy)phenyl-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one

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In a recent paper, McCormick *et al.*¹ reported the isolation of 8-C-prenyl-2'-methoxy-5,7,4'-trihydroxyflavanone from *Wyethia glabra*. Its structure was deduced on the basis of spectral evidences. We